

Dentinogenic Ghost Cell Tumor

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ABSTRACT

Context: Dentinogenic Ghost Cell Tumor (DGCT), a solid variant of the Calcifying Odontogenic Cyst (COC), is an uncommon odontogenic neoplasm occurring predominantly in later life with locally aggressive behavior characterized by ameloblastoma-like islands of aberrant keratinization of odontogenic epithelium in the form of ghost cells in association with dysplastic dentin. It accounts for only 2–14% of all COCs. Case Report: We report a case of 21 year old male patient with chief complaint of swelling in left upper back tooth region since 4-5 months and histopathologically characterized by ghost cell with strands and cluster of odontogenic epithelium in mature connective tissue stroma. associated with in dentinoid formation are some areas. Conclusion: The present case of 21-year-old male was diagnosed as DGCT, a timorous form of COC, due to its characteristic histological features; numerous ghost cells and dentinoid material.

KEY WORDS: calcifying, odontogenic cyst, aberrant keratinization, dentinogenic ghost cell tumor, dysplastic dentin

INTRODUCTION:

The former description of dentinogenic ghost cell tumor (DGCT) was proposed by Fejerskov and Krogh^[1] in 1972. They used the term ‘calcifying ghost cell odontogenic tumor.’ In 1981, Praetorius et al.^[2] recommended the term ‘dentinogenic ghost cell tumor.’ They suggested this term due to the formation of dentinoid in relation to the epithelial islands, which was a very prominent trait and because the ghost cells were found to be of altering degrees. The dentinogenic ghost cell tumor (DGCT) is an infrequent odontogenic neoplasm, regarded as a solid alternative of the calcifying odontogenic cyst (COC). Only 2–14% of COC are solid tumors and are considered to be DGCTs^[3]. It is characterized by ameloblastomatous odontogenic epithelium, existence of ghost cells and dentinoid material. Chiefly seen in older age group and can ensue either as a central (intraosseous) lesion or peripheral (extraosseous in the soft tissues) lesion^[4].

The calcifying odontogenic cyst (COC) was

first described in 1962 by Gorlin *et al.* as a split entity of odontogenic origin^[5]. COC, also referred to as calcifying ghost cell odontogenic cyst (CGCOC), is a varied lesion active either as cystic or solid alternative^[2]. Widely held of CGCOC (85%) are cystic in nature, and clinically may come about as a central (85%) or peripheral (15%) lesion. Central lesions frequently present as asymptomatic bony expansion, despite the fact that peripheral lesions are seen as sessile or pedunculated smooth surfaced masses^[6]. Due to the piece of evidence that all CGCOC lesions are not cystic, and the genetic behavior is often not steady with a cyst, there has constantly been a storm as to whether COC is a cyst or a tumor. The dentinogenic ghost cell tumor (DGCT), regarded as a solid alternative of the COC. DGCT can show evidence of either a benign or a malignant outline or can endure malignant transformation^[7].

The existing WHO classification of 2005 recognizes DGCT as the early solid variant of COC (type II).

CASE REPORT:

A 21 year old male patient reported to the outpatient department of Oral Pathology & Microbiology, Institute of Dental Sciences, Bareilly, with chief complaint of swelling in left upper back tooth region since 4-5 months which gradually

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Figure 1: Solitary, exophytic, sessile, soft tissue mass, pinkish red in color present on left maxillary posterior tooth region.

Figure 2: (Under Scanner view) Two pieces of tissue with odontogenic epithelium proliferating predominantly in plexiform pattern with mature connective tissue stroma in background. In some areas follicles and islands of odontogenic epithelium are also visible.

increased to the present size. The patient also had habit of keeping tobacco quid with lime and extraorally no obvious findings were noted. On intraoral examination a solitary, exophytic, sessile, globular soft tissue mass was present on maxillary posterior tooth region, extending mesiodistally from 23 to 24 regions, and measured 1 cm in its greatest dimension. (Figure. 1) The color of the overlying mucosa was pinkish red. The surface was irregular with an area of ulceration, covered with necrotic slough. The growth was firm in consistency and non-tender on palpation and was provisionally diagnosed as reactive or neoplastic growth. Histopathologically it is characterized by ghost cells with strand and cluster of odontogenic

epithelium in mature connective tissue stroma associated with in dentinoid formation some areas (Figure 2).

DISCUSSION:

According to the WHO^[7] the spectrum of odontogenic ghost cell tumors comprises DGCT, calcifying cystic odontogenic tumor (CCOT) and the ghost cell odontogenic carcinoma (GCOC). Based on a research of 215 COCs carried out by Buchner et al, who found that COC represents 1–2% of all odontogenic tumors and of these only 2–14% were solid tumors, considered to be DGCTs. DGCT is the solid, clinicopathologic variant of CCOT as COC

Figure 3: (Under Low power View) In some areas follicles and islands of odontogenic epithelium are visible with areas of ghost cells and mass of dentinoid material.

Figure 4: (Under Higher magnification): The odontogenic epithelium in some places, show cuboidal to columnar cells with dark hyperchromatic nucleus arranged in palisaded pattern (suggestive of ameloblast like cells). Associated stellate reticulum like tissue is appreciated. In some areas, ballooned and ovoid eosinophilic cells suggestive of “ghost cells” are visible. Few ghost cells show nuclear remnants with blurred outlines.

which was first described by Gorlin et al.^[8] However, Fejerskov and Krogh^[1] 1972 were of the opinion that the term COC is not entirely appropriate, for various reasons given below and suggested the term “calcifying ghost cell odontogenic tumor.”:

a) The presence of the ghost cells which may subsequently show calcification; b) The possibility of cystic degeneration taking place in the center of proliferating epithelial islands rather than epithelial changes developing in a preexisting cyst wall; c) Growth proliferative potentiality of some lesions giving rise to lesions of considerable size.

In 1981, Praetorius et al.^[9] suggested the term

“DGCT” because of the presence of ghost cells and abundant dentinoid material. The WHO, in 2005, defined DGCT as, 'A locally invasive neoplasm characterized by ameloblastoma like islands of epithelial cells in a mature connective tissue stroma. Aberrant keratinization may be found in the form of ghost cells in association with varying amounts of dysplastic dentin.'^[7] DGCT may occur as an intraosseous lesion (Type 1, 83%) and less commonly as an extraosseous peripheral lesion arising in the gingiva or alveolar mucosa (Type 2, 17%)^[4]. The age may range from 12 to 75 years (mean 50 years) with slight male predilection. The present case was seen in

a male patient aged 21 years. The peripheral type occurs significantly later in life than the central type^[4]. DGCT may occur in any tooth bearing area or the edentulous region of the jaws^[9,10].

Intraosseous lesions predominantly occur in first molar to canine region^[3]. The present case was noted in maxillary left posterior region. The size of the intraosseous DGCT varies from 1 to more than 10 cm in diameter and is usually asymptomatic. The clinical signs of intraosseous DGCT variants may include expansion of the jaw, clinically visible swelling and obliteration of the maxillary sinus or infiltration of the soft tissues. Swelling can be painful or painless and occasionally accompanied by pus discharge, tooth displacement or mobility^[11]. The present case which represented clinically as a soft tissue overgrowth is not a common finding.

To the best of our knowledge, only one case with similar findings has been reported^[10]. The DGCT can be asymptomatic and can also present itself as coincidental radiographic finding during routine patient examination. It appears radiographically as a radiolucent, radiopaque or mixed lesion depending on the amount of calcification. Lesions can be unilocular or multilocular with either well-defined or ill-demarcated margins. Root resorption, displacement of adjacent teeth and presence of impacted teeth have been reported^[10,11].

The predominant location for peripheral type is posterior portion of mandible (73%) and appears as exophytic nodules confined to the gingival mucosa in dentate patients or the alveolar mucosa in edentulous patients^[4]. This lesion may be confused with reactive or inflammatory lesions of gingiva, such as peripheral giant cell granuloma, pyogenic granuloma, irritation fibroma, epulis or parulis^[12]. Very often it is of 0.5 cm to 1 cm in size with little variations^[8]. Mild erosion or the saucerisation of the underlying cortical bone may be seen in 20% of cases^[9].

HISTOGENESIS:

The histogenetic derivation of DGCT has been attributed to cell rests of Serre or the surface epithelium but currently remains unclear^[13]. Missense mutation on codon 3 (ACT → TCT), i.e., threonine to serine of β catenin gene suggests that β catenin plays an important role in the tumorigenesis of DGCT by an improper differentiation process coordinated by Wnt signaling pathway^[14].

CONCLUSION:

DGCT is an uncommon odontogenic neoplasm, regarded as a solid variant of the COC. Only 2–14% of COC are solid tumors considered to be DGCTs. A case of central DGCT in a 21 year old male patient with clinical presentation as a soft tissue growth over the alveolar ridge is reported here.

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